

Ten new species in *Papuliscala* de Boury, 1911 (Gastropoda, Epitoniidae) from the South Azorean Seamount Chain

Diez nuevas especies de *Papuliscala* de Boury, 1911 (Gastropoda, Epitoniidae) de la cadena de montañas submarinas del sur de Azores

Leon HOFFMAN*,¹, Serge GOFAS** & André FREIWALD*

Recibido el 21-X-2019. Aceptado el 8-XI-2019

ABSTRACT

Eleven species of the genus *Papuliscala* de Boury, 1911 (Epitoniidae Berry, 1910) were collected on the South Azorean Seamount Chain (SASC), ten of them described as new: *Papuliscala dictyophora* n. sp., *P. seamountae* n. sp., *P. platoensis* n. sp., *P. caroliensae* n. sp., *P. luuki* n. sp., *P. daani* n. sp., *P. meteorica* n. sp., *P. atlantisa* n. sp., *P. vixcostata* n. sp. and *P. mikra* n. sp. The distributions of these new taxa are probably restricted to summital plateaus and bathyal slopes of the SASC. Some of them form regional radiations within *Papuliscala* with shared morphological characteristics.

RESUMEN

Once especies del género *Papuliscala* de Boury, 1911 (Epitoniidae Berry, 1910) fueron recolectadas en la cadena de montañas submarinas del sur de Azores (SASC), siendo diez de ellas descritas como nuevas: *Papuliscala dictyophora* n. sp., *P. seamountae* n. sp., *P. platoensis* n. sp., *P. caroliensae* n. sp., *P. luuki* n. sp., *P. daani* n. sp., *P. meteorica* n. sp., *P. atlantisa* n. sp., *P. vixcostata* n. sp. y *P. mikra* n. sp. Las distribuciones de estos nuevos taxones probablemente estén restringidas a la parte alta y laderas batiales de la SASC. Algunas de estas especies forman radiaciones regionales dentro de *Papuliscala* con características morfológicas compartidas.

INTRODUCTION

This paper reviews species of the genus *Papuliscala* de Boury, 1911 (Epitoniidae Berry, 1910). These species were encountered in sediment samples gathered during three cruises (GOFAS, 1993; GEORGE, 2010; FRANK, 2018) to seven seamounts in the South Azorean Seamount Chain (SASC) (Figs. 1-2). The SASC is located about 500 km south of the Azores and about 1500 km west of the NW African coastline. Our studies con-

centrated on the biodiversity and development of deep-water coral (DWC) habitats on the bathyal slopes in the SASC. The results in various molluscan groups, like this paper, are a spin-off of these general efforts on DWC biocoenoses. In a companion paper of this volume, HOFFMAN, GOFAS & FREIWALD (2020) give an outline of the SASC seamounts and an overview of important publications on Mollusca from the SASC.

* Marine Research Department, Senckenberg am Meer, Südstrand 40, Wilhelmshaven, Germany.

** Departamento de Biología Animal, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Málaga, Málaga, Spain.

¹ Corresponding author: leon.hoffman@senckenberg.de

Figure 1. Location of the SASC in the NE Atlantic Ocean. Bathymetry data GEBCO.
 Figura 1. Ubicación de la SASC en el Océano Atlántico NE. Datos de batimetría GEBCO.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The methodology and data of the sampling area (Fig. 1) are detailed in this same volume (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2020). Coordinates in degrees and minutes from original station lists were here converted to decimal degrees.

We have given special attention to the protoconch to infer the mode of development and the possible dispersal capacity of the species. This relationship is well established for representatives of most caenogastropod families (see MILEIKOVSKY, 1971; SHUTO, 1974; LIMA & LUTZ, 1990; NÜTZEL, 2014; among many others). Therefore, we follow here the classical terminology for early ontogenetic features of the shells in gastropods and their relationship with the mode of development (i.e. JABLONSKI & LUTZ, 1980; LIMA & LUTZ, 1990; CASTELIN *ET AL.*, 2011; NÜTZEL, 2014):

The first developmental stage of the shell is the protoconch I (embryonic

shell), secreted by the shell gland of the embryo inside the egg capsule. The second stage is the protoconch II (larval shell), added by the mantle of the free veliger after hatching. The teleoconch is the part formed by the mantle of the crawling juvenile after metamorphosis.

In planktotrophic development, veliger larvae hatch from the egg capsules without maternal food and spend some variable time in the water column feeding on phytoplankton. The species with this type of development show a dome protoconch I and tall protoconch II of more than one whorl (multispiral protoconch) and they are capable of long-distance dispersal.

The non-planktotrophic development is generally subdivided into two subtypes:

Without a free pelagic phase (normally called direct development). Then the shell consists of only two successive stages (protoconch I and teleoconch),

Figure 2. Location maps in SASC. A: distribution of *Papuliscala praelonga* indicated by blue squares, *P. dictyophora* n. sp. by red dots, *P. seamountae* n. sp. by yellow diamonds, *P. platoensis* n. sp. by green triangles; B: *P. caroliense* n. sp. by red dots, *P. luuki* n. sp. by yellow diamonds, *P. daani* n. sp. by green triangles; C: *P. meteorica* n. sp. by red dots, *P. atlantisa* n. sp. by yellow diamonds; D: *P. vixcostata* n. sp. by red dots, *P. mikro* n. sp. by green triangles. Bathymetry data GEBCO, depth contours 1000 m.

Figura 2. Mapas de ubicación en SASC. A: distribución de *Papuliscala praelonga* indicada por cuadrados azules, *P. dictyophora* n. sp. por puntos rojos, *P. seamountae* n. sp. por rombos amarillos, *P. platoensis* n. sp. por triángulos verdes; B: *P. caroliense* n. sp. por puntos rojos, *P. luuki* n. sp. por rombos amarillos, *P. daani* n. sp. por triángulos verdes; C: *P. meteorica* n. sp. por puntos rojos, *P. atlantisa* n. sp. por rombos amarillos; D: *P. vixcostata* n. sp. por puntos rojos, *P. mikro* n. sp. por triángulos verdes. Datos de batimetría GEBCO, isobatas 1000 m.

without protoconch II, and dispersal seems to be very restricted in species with this type of development.

Larvae are released to the water column in an advanced stage, giving rise to a short pelagic non-feeding stage before metamorphosis and settlement (normally called lecithotrophic development). The shell of such species is characterized by a bulbous protoconch I and a short protoconch II (less than one whorl) which continues with the teleoconch with a sharp transition. These species have a variable dispersal capacity but not at long distances.

SYSTEMATIC RESULTS

MOLLUSCA, GASTROPODA, CAENOGASTROPODA, EPITONIOIDEA Berry, 1910

Family EPITONIIDAE Berry, 1910

Epitonioida Berry, 1910 has been a popular conchological topic for centuries. Consequently, nomenclature and systematics of Epitonioida have been subject to many changes. NÜTZEL (1998) reviewed the Ptenoglossa and separated Nystiellidae as a different family from Epitoniidae. Global reviews of Recent Epitoniidae and Nystiellidae were compiled by WEIL, BROWN & NEVILLE (1999) and by BROWN & NEVILLE (2015). A

Species with both direct and lecithotrophic development show a paucispiral protoconch.

Abbreviations:

Institutions: MNHN - Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle; SMF - Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt; SaM - Senckenberg am Meer.

Cruises: M151 - R/V Meteor Cruise 151; POS397 - R/V Poseidon cruise 397; R/V - research vessel; SMT2 - R/V Suroit cruise SEAMOUNT-2,

Morphology: H - height (*alto*); W - width (*ancho*), maximum diameter.

review of Epitoniidae, including Nystiellinae as a subfamily, from the NE Atlantic Ocean was carried out by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1986). Nevertheless, TAKANO & KANO (2014), in a molecular phylogeny based on 28S and COI genes, found the nystiellid genus *Opaliopsis* nested between the epitoniids *Opalia* and *Epitonium*. This led BOUCHET ET AL. (2017) to place Nystiellidae in synonymy of Epitoniidae.

Genus *Papuliscala* de Boury, 1911

Type taxon: *Acirsa praelonga* Jeffreys, 1877 by original designation.

DE BOURY (1911: 220) did not give a diagnosis for the genus. BOUCHET & WARÉN (1986: 494) used the genus for Atlantic deep-water species with a sculpture of broad, non-lamellar axial ribs and strong spiral cords, a distinct basal disc, an angular aperture, and a paucispiral larval shell.

Noteworthy reviews on *Papuliscala* were given by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1986) on the NE Atlantic and by PIMENTA, ANDRADE & ABSALÃO (2018) on the continental slope and the Rio

Grande Rise off Brazil. Six extant species are known in the Atlantic basin: *Papuliscala praelonga* (Jeffreys, 1877), *P. elongata* (Watson, 1881), *P. cerithielloides* Bouchet & Warén, 1986, *P. tavianii* Bouchet & Warén, 1986, *P. diminuta* Castellanos, Rolán & Bartolotta, 1987 and *P. lydiae* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2017. Only two additional species, *P. japonica* (Okutani, 1964) and *P. superlata* (Finlay, 1930) are reported from the rest of the world (WoRMS editorial board, 2019). In this paper we add ten new species.

Figures 3-6. *Papuliscala praelonga*, Irving Seamount, SMT2/DW238, H 6.8 mm, W 1.9 mm, protoconch I H 0.32, W 0.36 mm, protoconch II H 0.59 mm, W 0.40 mm.

Figuras 3-6. Papuliscala praelonga, Banco Irving, SMT2/DW238, H 6,8 mm, W 1,9 mm, protoconcha I H 0,32, W 0,36 mm, protoconcha II H 0,59 mm, W 0,40 mm.

Papuliscala praelonga (Jeffreys, 1877) (Figs. 2A, 3-6)

Acirsa praelonga Jeffreys, 1877: 241, pl. 10 fig. 11.

Papuliscala praelonga: BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1986: 496, fig. 1662.

Type material: BOUCHET & WARÉN (1986) selected as lectotype the specimen in BMNH (85.11.5.1918) from *Porcupine* sta. 16, figured by Jeffreys (1884: pl. 10 fig. 11) and treated by Warén (1980: 30) as "holotype", paralectotypes from *Valorous* sta. 12 in USNM (182735).

Material examined: Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW238, 32.288 °N - 27.538 °W, 890 - 900 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, one shell (MNHN-IM-2014-7961, Figs. 3-6).

Type locality: off western Portugal, 39°55'N, 09°56'W, 1800 m.

Distribution: Amphi-Atlantic, 18 - 65 °N, 713 - 2650 m. BOUCHET & WARÉN (1986) identified as *P. praelonga* the two paralectotypes of *P. elongata* (Watson, 1881) from Challenger sta. 24, 18°38' N, 65°03' W, 718 m. Here recorded for the first time from the SASC (Fig. 2A).

Remarks: The species is characterised by weak axial undulations, weak spiral cordlets, high spire (apex angle 15°), at least 20 axial ribs on the last and penultimate whorls and two-staged protoconch. The base of the whorl is flattened.

Papuliscala dictyophora n. sp. (Figs. 2A, 7-12)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35196, Figs. 10-12) from dredge SMT2/DW182, 16-I-1993; paratypes 142 shells (MNHN-IM-2000-35197) from type locality.

Other material examined: Atlantis Seamount - M151/23404, 33.971 °N - 30.206 °W, 677 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 17 shells; M151/23408, 33.996 °N - 30.177 °W, 617 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 28 shells. Tyro

Seamount - SMT2/DW275, 34.058 °N - 28.302 °W, 1590 – 1665 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, one shell. Plato Seamount - SMT2/DW240, 33.205 °N - 29.032 °W, 565 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, three shells; SMT2/DW242, 33.197 °N - 28.949 °W, 690-710 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, seven shells; SMT2/DW247, 33.228 °N - 29.588 °W, 580-625 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, three shells. Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, four shells. Great Meteor Seamount - SMT2/DW166, 29.600 °N, 28.380 °W, 575 m, 13-I-1993, dredge, one live taken specimen; POS397/91-10, 30.083 °N, 28.633 °W, 310 m, 15-III-2010, grab, two shells; POS397/92-3, 30.084 °N - 28.566 °W, 301 m, 15-III-2010, grab, one shell; POS397/92-5, 30.017 °N - 28.533 °W, 286 m, 15-III-2010, grab, one shell; POS397/92-6, 30.017 °N - 28.533 °W, 288 m, 15-III-2010, grab, one shell; POS397/96-7, 29.950 °N - 28.633 °W, 309 m, 15-III-2010, grab, one shell; POS397/98-1, 30.084 °N - 28.500 °W, 309 m, 17-III-2010, grab, four shells; POS397/102-3, 29.950 °N - 28.567 °W, 285 m, 19-III-2010, grab, one shell; POS397/106-2, 29.816 °N - 28.433 °W, 300 m, 19-III-2010, grab, two shells; POS397/109-5, 29.817 °N - 28.567 °W, 307 m, 20-III-2010, grab, three shells; POS397/114-5, 29.683 °N - 28.434 °W, 288 m, 21-III-2010, grab, six shells; POS397/114-6, 29.683 °N - 28.434 °W, 289 m, 21-III-2010, grab, six shells; M151/23419-2, 29.750 °N - 28.533 °W, 319 m, 24-X-2018, grab, seven shells; M151/23425-R6, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 944 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell; M151/23425-R9, 29.568 °N - 28.339 °W, 855 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, two shells. Little Meteor Seamount - M151/23436, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 852 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 6 shells; M151/23437, 29.654 °N - 29.014 °W, 811 m, 27-X-2018, grab, two shells; M151/23438, 29.655 °N - 29.004 °W, 464 m, 27-X-2018, grab, one shell; M151/23440, 29.645 °N - 28.975 °W, 284 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 2 shells (MNHN-IM-2014-7962, Figs. 7–9), 51 shells; M151/23441, 29.633 °N - 28.976 °W, 282 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 14 shells; M151/23442, 29.633 °N - 28.983 °W, 274 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 42 shells.

Type locality: Hyères Seamount, 31.387 °N - 28.892 °W, 480 m.

Etymology: *dictyophora* refers to the sculpture: net-bearing in Greek.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 10–12): Shell with a raised, regularly growing spire, strong, stepped outline with coarsely reticulated sculpture, blunt apex, translucent white. H 4.6 mm, W 1.6 mm, spire angle 17°.

Protoconch - Two stages. Protoconch I: raised nucleus, $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, smooth, H 0.30 mm, W 0.30 mm. Protoconch II: one raised convex whorl, axial fine flexuous ribs, sharp flexuous lip, H 0.52 mm, W 0.35 mm. Transition to teleoconch clear by change in sculpture (Figs. 8, 9 of shells from Little Meteor Seamount).

Teleoconch - Spire raised with 7 angular whorls, all whorls with strongly reticulated sculpture. Suture shallow, impressed.

All whorls with three spiral cords; one strong cord at base of sloping shoulder, one finer cord at the periphery and one strong cord at the lower suture. First whorl with 12 axial ribs, all remaining whorls with 14 axial ribs, straight, slightly prosocline. Spiral cords overrun axial ones with strong nodules at intersections. Shoulder area flattened and keeled. Periphery slightly convex. Fine growth lines in areas between ribs.

On body whorl, width of spiral cord about 0.07 mm, width of axial rib 0.11 mm, inter-rib rectangular area height about 0.18 mm, width 0.22 mm. Axial ribs at 15° with shell axis (Fig. 11).

Base of body whorl flattened, keeled at basal cord, slightly concave below. Faint spiral lines near columella. Strong growth lines. Umbilicus absent.

Aperture 20% of shell height, rounded at the base of columella, somewhat truncated abapically, weakly angular adapically (Fig. 12). Columellar lip narrow, clearly demarcated from body whorl (Fig. 12). Outer lip (damaged) sharp, slightly prosocline. Columellar callus smooth, thinning on parietal side. Inside smooth.

Soft parts (based on specimen from DW 166): Cephalic tentacles large, slightly tapering but rounded at tip, widely separated, with mouth on a short bilobed bulge between tentacles; eyes moderately large, embedded at the base of tentacles, hardly bulging. Foot rather massive, truncated anteriorly, tapering posteriorly, opercular lobe thick. A large pallial tentacle on the right side, inserted beneath the whorl shoulder. Colour entirely white except for black eyes.

Figures 7–12. *Papuliscala dictyophora* n. sp. 7, 8: Little Meteor Seamount, M151/23440, H 3.5 mm, W 1.3 mm, protoconch I H 0.29 mm, W 0.29 mm, protoconch II H 0.52 mm, W 0.33 mm; 9: same locality, protoconch I H 0.33 mm, W 0.30 mm, protoconch II H 0.51 mm, W 0.35 mm; 10–12: holotype, Hyères Seamount, SMT2/DW182, H 4.6 mm, W 1.6 mm. Large arrow-head = lip of protoconch I, small arrow = lip of protoconch II.

Figuras 7-12. Papuliscala dictyophora n. sp. 7, 8: Pequeño Banco Meteor, M151/23440, H 3,5 mm, W 1,3 mm, protoconcha I H 0,29 mm, W 0,29 mm, protoconcha II H 0,52 mm, W 0,33 mm; 9: protoconcha I H 0,33 mm, W 0,30 mm, protoconcha II H 0,51 mm, W 0,35 mm; 10-12: holotipo, Banco Hyères, SMT2/DW182, H 4,6 mm, W 1,6 mm. Punta de flecha grande = labio de protoconcha I, flecha pequeña = labio de protoconcha II.

Variability: Low variability. Height up to 6 mm.

Distribution: SASC, latitude range 29.4 – 34.0 °N, longitude range 28.2 – 30.2 °W, and bathymetric range 274 – 1665 m (Fig. 2A).

Remarks: *Papuliscala elongata* (Watson, 1881), described from the Azores (see BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1986, fig. 1160, lectotype and PIMENTA *ET AL.*, 2018, fig. 15) has four spiral cords (including the suprasutural cord prolonged on the last whorl, about 18 axial ribs and a rounded base whereas our specimens (Figs. 15, 18) have three spiral cords, 14 axial ribs that are

more pronounced, and a flattened (keeled) base. A most similar species is *Papuliscala tavianii* Bouchet & Warén, 1986; this species has three spiral cords but a different protoconch with very strong axial ribs in the part preceding the teleoconch. Another similar species is *Papuliscala seamountae* n. sp. but this species has a protoconch with a single stage, a broader spire, rounded whorls and a flared base (Figs. 13, 14).

Our finds were empty shells in bioclastic sediment containing coral remains, and a single live-taken specimen.

Figures 13-15. *Papuliscala seamountae* n. sp., holotype, Little Meteor Seamount, M151/23440, H 2.4 mm, W 1.0 mm, protoconch H 0.30 mm, W 0.27 mm. Arrowhead = lip of protoconch.

Figuras 13-15. Papuliscala seamountae n. sp., holotipo, Pequeño Banco Meteor, M151/23440, H 2,4 mm, W 1,0 mm, protoconcha H 0,30 mm, W 0,27 mm. Punta de flecha = labio de la protoconcha.

Papuliscala seamountae n. sp. (Figs. 2A, 13-15)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35198, Figs. 13-15) from grab M151/23440, 27-X-2018. Paratypes from Little Meteor Seamount, M151/23436, 29.654 °N – 29.015 °W, 852 m, 27-X-2018, grab, 10 shells (MNHN-IM-2000-35199); M151/23438, 29.655 °N – 29.004 °W, 464 m, 27-X-2018, grab, three shells (SMF351089).

Other material examined: Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, 16 shells. Great Meteor Seamount - M151/23419-2, 29.750 °N - 28.533 °W, 319 m, 24-X-2018, grab, one shell; M151/23425-R4, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 945 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, one shell; M151/23425-R9, 29.568 °N - 28.339 °W, 855 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, five shells.

Type locality: Little Meteor Seamount, 29.645 °N – 28.975 °W, 284 m, in bioclastic sand with dead solitary corals.

Etymology: *seamountae* refers to the SEAMOUNT-2 expedition conducted by the second author that enabled a thorough study of the molluscan fauna of the SASC.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 13-15): Shell with a raised spire with rounded whorls, solid, outline with coarsely reticulated sculpture, blunt apex, colour translucent white. H 2.4 mm, W 1.0 mm, spire angle 27°.

Protoconch – Paucispiral without protoconch II, globular nucleus, one whorl, surface smooth. Lip slightly convex, nearly orthocone. H 0.30 mm, W 0.27 mm. Transition to teleoconch clear by change in sculpture (Fig. 14).

Teleoconch - Spire raised with 4 ¾ whorls, all whorls with reticulated sculpture of raised and regularly-spaced prosocline straight axial ribs overrunning raised spiral cords, thickened at the

crossings (Figs. 13, 15). Suture shallow, impressed.

Each whorl with three spiral cords with lowest cord at suture partly covered by subsequent whorl (Fig. 15). Top spiral cord forms a weak keel to convex shoulder area. Between first and second spiral cord a vertical flat area. Second spiral cord with weak keel above flattened lower whorl face. First to fourth whorls with 14 axial ribs, the last one with 16 ribs. On body whorl, width of spiral cord about 0.07 mm, width axial rib 0.09 mm, inter-rib rectangular area height about 0.18 mm, width 0.16 mm. Axial ribs at 17° with shell axis (Fig. 15).

Figures 16-18. *Papuliscala platoensis* n. sp., holotype, Plato Seamount, SMT2/DW242, H 3.8 mm, W 1.6 mm, protoconch H 0.51 mm, W 0.40 mm. Arrowhead = lip of protoconch.

Figuras 16-18. *Papuliscala platoensis* n. sp., holotipo, Banco Plato, SMT2/DW242, H 3,8 mm, W 1,6 mm, protoconcha H 0,51 mm, W 0,40 mm. Punta de flecha = labio de la protoconcha.

Lowest spiral cord at the level of the suture with keel demarcating slightly concave base of whorl; axial ribs absent on basal area; covered with many growth lines. Umbilicus absent.

Aperture 22% of shell height, nearly circular, flared at base (Fig. 15). Columella slightly curved, columellar lip definite, outer lip sharp, straight, prosocline, union with penultimate whorl nearly horizontal and partly covering lowest spiral cord. Inside smooth.

Variability: Height up to 3 mm. Slight variation in apex angle.

Distribution: Only known from Irving-, Little Meteor- and Great Meteor Seamounts, SASC, 29.5 – 32.3 °N, 27.5 – 29.1 °W, 284 – 945 m (Fig. 2A).

Remarks: Distinct features are the combination of a small paucispiral protoconch, rounded whorls, and flared lip at the base. Refer to the remarks under *Papuliscala dictyophora* n. sp. (Figs. 7-12) for differences with this species and with *P. elongata* (Watson, 1881).

Papuliscala platoensis n. sp. (Figs. 2A, 16–18)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35200, Figs. 16–18) from dredge SMT2/DW242, 31-I-1993.

Type locality: Plato Seamount, 33.197 °N – 28.949 °W, 690-710 m.

Etymology: *platoensis* is named after the type locality: Plato Seamount.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 16–18): Shell with a raised spire, solid, coarsely reticulated sculpture, blunt apex, colour cream white. H 3.8 mm, W 1.6 mm, spire angle 25°.

Protoconch - Paucispiral, raised globular, 1 ½ whorls without protoconch II. H

0.51 mm, W 0.40 mm. Transition to teleoconch clear by prosocline varix (Fig. 17).

Teleoconch - Raised spire with five rounded whorls. Suture shallow, impressed. First whorl initially smooth; at ½ whorl four cords emerge, three strong cords on the whorl surface and

one partly covered by lower suture. Oblique, straight axial ribs emerge on second whorl, the third and fourth with 16 ribs, the last one with 20 ribs. A fifth spiral cord on shoulder of body whorl. On body whorl, width of spiral cord about 0.08 mm, width of axial rib 0.03 mm, inter-rib rectangular area height about 0.12 mm, width 0.17 mm. Axial rib angle 21° with spire axis. Inter-rib areas with few irregular growth stages and micro-nodules (diameter 1 µm, Fig. 18).

Lowest spiral cord at the level of the suture with weak keel demarcating slightly concave base of whorl; three faint spiral cordlets and growth stages on base body whorl. Umbilicus absent.

Aperture 25% of shell height, pointed at base of weakly curved columella (Fig.

16). Columellar callus demarcated from basal whorl area. Outer lip sharp, prosocline, sloping at its union with penultimate whorl. Inside smooth.

Variability: Unknown.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality (Fig. 2A).

Remarks: Distinct features are the dominant spiral sculpture, the micro-sculpture and the tall protoconch. *Papulisca* *cerithioides* Bouchet & Warén, 1986 is similar but this species has seven spiral cords and approximately 30 axial ribs on the body whorl. *P. luuki* n. sp. is taller with a finer sculpture and flexuous ribs, *P. seamountensis* n. sp. has a coarser sculpture with three spiral cords on all whorls, *P. lydiae* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2017 lacks the basal structure and has a flatter sculpture.

Papulisca carolienae n. sp. (Figs. 2B, 19-25)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35201, Figs. 22-25) and 72 paratypes (shells, MNHN-IM-2000-35202) from dredge SMT2/DW242, 31-I-1993.

Other material examined: Atlantis Seamount - M151/23404, 33.971 °N -30.206 °W, 677 m, 21-X-2018, grab in bioclastic sand with coral fragments, figured shell (MNHN-IM-2014-7963, Fig. 19), figured shell (MNHN-IM-2014-7964, Figs. 20-21), 13 shells (SaM); M151/23408, 33.996 °N -30.177 °W, 617 m, 21-X-2018, grab, one shell. Plato Seamount - SMT2/DW240, 33.205 °N - 29.032 °W, 565 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW250, 33.210 °N - 29.287 °W, 1450-1500 m, 01-II-1993, dredge, 13 shells. Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, seven shells; SMT2/DW238, 32.288 °N - 27.538 °W, 890-900 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, one shell. Hyères Seamount - SMT2/DW182, 31.387 °N - 28.892 °W, 480 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, 42 shells.

Type locality: Plato Seamount, 33.197 °N - 28.949 °W, 690 – 710 m.

Etymology: *carolienae* refers to the daughter Carolien of the senior author.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 22-25): Shell with a raised spire, fragile, outline with sharp reticulated sculpture, blunt apex, colour cream white. H 2.1 mm, W 1.0 mm, spire angle 28°.

Protoconch - Paucispiral, 1 ¼ whorls without protoconch II, raised, flattened at the nucleus, smooth. Lip convex, prosocline. H 0.28 mm, W 0.29 mm. Transition to teleoconch clear by change in sculpture (Fig. 21 of a shell from Atlantis Seamount).

Teleoconch - Spire raised with 4 ½ rounded whorls, all whorls with reticulated sculpture of sharp and irregularly-spaced axial ribs overrunning broad and flat spiral cords, thickened at the crossings (Fig. 23). Suture rather deep.

Six spiral cords on all spire whorls. Oblique, slightly flexuous axial ribs about 30 on first and second whorl and on last whorl, 32 on third whorl and up to 34 on fourth whorl. There are 3-6 growth lines visible between axial ribs creating rough inter-rib texture and irregular markings on the spiral cords. On body whorl, width spiral cord about 0.03 mm, width axial rib 0.01 mm, inter-rib rectangular area height about 0.11 mm, width 0.08 mm (Fig. 23).

Lowest spiral cord on the body whorl in prolongation of the suture, forming a weak keel demarcating slightly concave base of body whorl; axial ribs very weakly prolonged on the base. Basal area covered with many growth lines and four spiral cords. Umbilicus absent.

Figures 19-25. *Papuliscala caroliensae* n. sp. 19: Atlantis Seamount, M151/23404, H 2.9 mm, W 1.2 mm; 20, 21: same locality, H 2.8 mm, W 1.1 mm, protoconch 0.41 mm, W 0.34 mm; 22-25: holotype, Plato Seamount, SMT2/DW242, H 2.1 mm, W 1.0 mm, protoconch H 0.28 mm, W 0.29 mm. Arrowhead = lip of the protoconch.

Figuras 19-25. Papuliscala caroliensae n. sp. 19: Banco Atlantis, M151/23404. 19. H 2,9 mm, W 1,2 mm; 20, 21: misma localidad, H 2,8 mm, W 1,1 mm, protoconcha 0,41 mm, W 0,34 mm; 22-25: holotipo, Banco Plato, SMT2/DW242, H 2,1 mm, W 1,0 mm, protoconcha H 0,28 mm, W 0,29 mm. Punta de flecha = labio de la protoconcha.

Aperture 22% of shell height, oblong (Fig. 22, 24). Columella flexuous, columellar lip definite, outer lip sharp, flexuous, nearly horizontal at its union with penultimate whorl where it covers the basal spiral cord. Inside smooth.

Variability: Height range of protoconch 0.28-0.41 mm. Number of axial ribs on the body whorl 24-34, number of axial ribs 6-7, rib spacing frequently irregular. Spiral cords on base of body whorl can be very faint. Spire angle range 22-28°. Height up to 3 mm.

Distribution: Only known from the Atlantis-, Irving-, Plato- and Hyères

Seamounts, northern SASC, 31.3 – 34.0 °N, 27.5 – 30.3 °W, 480 – 1500 m (Fig. 2B).

Remarks: Distinct features are the unique sculpture of flat spiral cords and thin axial ribs and rough inter-rib surface. A similar species is *Papuliscala cerithielloides* Bouchet & Warén, 1986, which was described from off Portugal but that species is larger, with well-developed flat axial ribs and spiral cords, nearly as thick as the interspaces whereas axial and spiral cords are less than half the interspaces in *P. caroliensae* n. sp. *Papuliscala dictyophora* n. sp. (Figs. 7-12) and *P. praelonga* (Jeffreys, 1877)

Figures 26-28. *Papuliscala luuki* n. sp., holotype, Great Meteor Seamount, M151/23425R6, H 4.3 mm, W 1.3 mm, protoconch H 0.34 mm, W 0.32 mm.

Figuras 26-28. *Papuliscala luuki* n. sp., holotipo, Gran Banco Meteor, M151/23425R6, H 4,3 mm, W 1,3 mm, protoconcha H 0,34 mm, W 0,32 mm.

(Figs. 3–6) have less axial ribs and spiral cords and a keel at the shoulder. *Papuliscala luuki* n. sp. (Figs. 26-28) has a higher

spire and rounded ribs, and has spiral cords prevalent over axials, contrary to the present species.

Papuliscala luuki n. sp. (Figs. 2B, 26-28)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35203, Figs. 26-28) and two paratype shells (SMF351090) from ROV sample M151/23425-R6, 25-X-2018.

Type locality: Great Meteor Seamount, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 944 m, in bioclastic sand with coral fragments.

Etymology: *luuki* is named after Luuk, the second son of the senior author.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 26-28): Shell with highly-raised spire, fragile, reticulated sculpture, blunt apex, colour cream white, H 4.3 mm, W 1.3 mm, spire angle 17°.

Protoconch (damaged) - Paucispiral, raised, 1 ¼ whorls without protoconch II, surface smooth. H 0.34 mm, W 0.32 mm. Clear transition to teleoconch by change in sculpture (Fig. 27, damaged shell).

Teleoconch - Spire raised with 7 ½ rounded whorls, all whorls with reticulated sculpture of raised thin, smooth and regularly-spaced axial ribs, raised, broad and smooth spiral cords, thickened at the crossings (Figs. 26, 28). Suture impressed.

Axial ribs flexuous, nearly vertical in their abapical part, about 26 on first and second whorl, up to 34 on fourth whorl and about 30 on the three last whorls. Four spiral cords on the first three whorls, 5 on the fourth whorl and 6 on the last three whorls. Numerous very fine growth lines visible between axial ribs; smooth inter-rib structure. On the body whorl, width of spiral cord about 0.03 mm, width of axial rib 0.01 mm, inter-rib rectangular area height about 0.15 mm, width 0.12 mm (Fig. 28).

Lowest spiral cord on whorl face at the level of the suture with weak keel demarcating concavely flattened base of whorl; axial ribs very weak on basal area. Basal

Figures 29-32. *Papuliscala daani* n. sp. 29, 30: holotype, Plato Seamount, SMT2/DW250. H 6.0 mm, W 2.7 mm; 31, 32: paratype, same locality, H 5.9 mm, W 2.3 mm, protoconch I, H 0.44 mm, W 0.44 mm, protoconch II, H 0.73 mm, W 0.52 mm. Arrow = lip of protoconch II.

Figuras 29-32. Papuliscala daani n. sp. 29, 30: holotipo, Banco Plato, SMT2/DW250, H 6,0 mm, W 2,7 mm; 31, 32: paratipo, misma localidad, H 5,9 mm, W 2,3 mm, protoconcha I, H 0,44 mm, W 0,44 mm, protoconcha II, H 0,73 mm, W 0,52 mm. Flecha = labio de la protoconcha II.

area with one inconspicuous and one clear spiral cord. Umbilicus absent.

Aperture 20% of shell height, oblong with flared base (Fig. 26). Columella curved, columellar lip clear, outer lip (damaged) flexuous, nearly horizontal at union with penultimate whorl, partly covering lowest spiral cord. Inside smooth.

Variability: The limited material does not allow assessing the variability.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality (Fig. 2B).

Remarks: Distinct features are the sculpture with raised broad spirals prevalent over the thin axial ribs and the highly-raised spire. A similar species is *Papuliscala cerithielloides* Bouchet & Warén, 1986 (Fig. 23) but that species has a broader outline and a rounded profile of the whorls. *P. praelonga* (Jeffreys, 1877) has a spiny shoulder cord and a base with fine spiral cordlets. Both *P. cerithielloides* and *P. carolienae* n. sp. differ clearly in having axial ribs prevalent over spiral cords.

Papuliscala daani n. sp. (Figs. 2B, 29-32)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35204, Figs. 29-30) and one paratype shell (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35205, Figs. 31-32) from dredge SMT2/DW250, 31-I-1993.

Type locality: Plato Seamount, 33.197 °N – 28.949 °W, 690 – 710 m.

Etymology: *daani* is named after the first son of the senior author: Daan.

Table I. *Papuliscala daani* n. sp. axial rib and spiral cord counts
 Tabla I. *Papuliscala daani* n. sp., recuento de costillas axiales y cordones espirales.

Whorl	1	2	3	4	5
Axial ribs	30	34	38	38	42
Spiral cords	6	6	7	9	11

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 29-30): Shell with a raised spire, deep suture, solid, finely reticulated sculpture, blunt apex, colour cream white. H 6.0 mm, W 2.7 mm, spire angle 31°.

Protoconch - Two-stage. Protoconch I, raised, smooth, one whorl, H 0.44 mm, W 0.44 mm. Protoconch II, fine, straight, with slightly-prosocline ribs, $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, terminating with flexuous varix. Transition to teleoconch clear by varix and change in sculpture (Fig. 31, paratype).

Teleoconch - Raised spire with 5 $\frac{1}{2}$ rounded whorls. Somewhat irregular pattern of dominant and flexuous axial ribs overrunning rounded spiral cords and channels of equal strength (Fig. 30). Number of axial ribs and spiral cords increasing with age (Table I). On body whorl, width spiral cord about 0.06 mm, width axial rib 0.05 mm, inter-rib rectangular area height about 0.06 mm, width 0.12 mm (Fig. 30). Axial rib angle 10° with spire axis. Inter-rib areas with micro-nodules (Fig. 30).

Axial ribs structure fades away on base of body whorl, six additional spiral

cords on base; smooth near columella. Umbilicus absent.

Aperture 30% of shell height, pointed at the base of weakly curved columella (Fig. 29). Columellar callus demarcated from previous whorl, almost detached. Outer lip semi-circular, with a sharp edge, slightly flexuous, horizontal at its union with penultimate whorl. Inside smooth.

Variability: Unknown.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality (Fig. 2B).

Remarks: A distinct feature is the finely reticulated sculpture. *Papuliscala cerithielloides* Bouchet & Warén, 1986 is similar in this respect but that species has a very regular sculpture of seven flattened spirals and approximately 30 flattened axial ribs, and has a narrower outline. From *Papuliscala caroliense* n. sp. the present species differs in having a more acute, tapering spire, a protoconch with nearly one more whorl, a more elevated profile and axial riblets in the larval shell preceding the teleoconch.

Papuliscala meteorica n. sp. (Figs. 2C, 33-39)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35206, Figs. 33-34), figured paratype 1 (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35207, Figs. 35, 36), one fragmentary paratype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35208), all from ROV sample M151/23425-R6, 25-X-2018. Paratypes, M151/23425-R9, 29.568 °N – 28.339 °W, 855 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, two shells (SMF351091).

Other material examined: Plato Seamount - SMT2/DW242, 33.197 °N - 28.949 °W, 690-710 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, four shells; SMT2/DW250, 33.210 °N - 29.287 °W, 1450-1500 m, 01-II-1993, dredge, four shells. Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW238, 32.288 °N - 27.538 °W, 890-900 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, one shell (MNHN-IM-2014-7965, Figs. 37-39). Little Meteor Seamount - M151/23434-R4, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 865 m, 27-X-2018, ROV, one shell; M151/23436, 29.654 °N – 29.015 °W, 852 m, 27-X-2018, grab, ten shells.

Type locality: Great Meteor Seamount, 29.565 °N – 28.339 °W, 944 m, in bioclastic coarse sand with coral rubble.

Etymology: *meteorica* refers to the type locality, the Great Meteor Seamount, as well as to the R/V Meteor, the ship that sampled the type locality.

Figures 33-39. *Papuliscala meteorica* n. sp. 33, 34: holotype, Great Meteor Seamount, M151/23425-R6, H 2.0 mm, W 1.4 mm, protoconch II H 0.46 mm, W 0.43 mm; 35, 36: paratype 1, same locality, H 2.4 mm, W 1.4 mm. 37-39: Irving Seamount, SMT2/DW238, H 4.1 mm, W 2.5 mm, protoconch II W 0.39 mm. Large arrowhead = lip of protoconch I, small arrow = lip of protoconch II.
 Figuras 33-39. *Papuliscala meteorica* n. sp. 33, 34: holotipo, Gran Banco Meteor, M151/23425-R6, H 2,0 mm, W 1,4 mm, protoconcha II H 0,46 mm, W 0,43 mm; 35, 36: paratipo 1, misma localidad, H 2,4 mm, W 1,4 mm, protoconcha II H 0,46 mm, W 0,43 mm; 37-39: Banco Irving, SMT2/DW238, H 4,1 mm, W 2,5 mm, protoconcha II W 0,39 mm. Punta de flecha grande = labio de protoconcha I, flecha pequeña = labio de protoconcha II.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 33-34): Shell with raised, regularly growing spire, fragile, outline with reticulated sculpture, open umbilicus, blunt apex, colour cream white, H 2.0 mm, W 1.4 mm, spire angle 45°.

Protoconch - Two stage. Protoconch I, ½ whorl, smooth. Protoconch II, ¼ whorl, six axial ribs (Fig. 34). Obliquely flattened and overhanging to one side. Lip convex. H 0.48 mm, W 0.48 mm.

Clear transition to teleoconch by change in sculpture (Fig. 34).

Teleoconch - Spire raised with 2 ¾ rounded whorls, all whorls with reticulated sculpture. Suture shallow, impressed.

First whorl with about 26 oblique axial ribs and three spiral cords on the lower whorl face, shoulder convex. Overrunning axial ribs thickened at the crossings. Numerous prosocline growth

lines visible. Axial ribs and growth lines at 25° with spire axis. Second whorl about 28 axial ribs and four spiral cords. The body whorl about 42 axial ribs and eight spiral cords, four above and four below the suture. 6 – 10 thin growth riblets between major axial ribs.

Umbilical area demarcated by weak keel and spiral cord. Umbilicus open, deep and tortuous; inside with prolonged axial ribs and one spiral cord.

Aperture 40% of shell height, rounded, weakly angular at abapical end (Figs. 33, 37). Columellar lip sharp. Outer lip (damaged), sharp, prosocline. A smooth callus covers the inner lip and columella, thinning on the parietal side. Inside smooth.

Variability: Protoconch width range 0.39 – 0.43 mm. Spire angle range 44 – 50°. Height up to 4.1 mm. Inter-axial-rib distance and number of radial ribs is somewhat variable.

Distribution: Plato-, Irving-, Great Meteor- and Little Meteor Seamounts, SASC, 29.5 – 33.3 °N, 28.3 – 29.3 °W, 690 – 1500 m (Fig. 2C).

Papuliscala atlantisa n. sp. (Figs. 2C, 40-44)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35209, Figs. 40-41), figured paratype 1 (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35210, Figs. 42-44), one large shell destroyed, 14 fragmentary paratype shells (SMF351092) from grab M151/23404, 21-X-2018.

Type locality: Atlantis Seamount, 33.971 °N – 30.206 °W, 677 m, in bioclastic coarse sand with coral rubble.

Etymology: *atlantisa* refers to the type locality: the Atlantis Seamount.

Description (based on the holotype, Figs. 40-41): Shell with a broad spire, fragile, reticulated sculpture, blunt apex, colour cream white, H 2.8 mm, W 2.3 mm, spire angle 70°.

Protoconch – Single stage, paucispiral, flattened nucleus, ¾ whorls without protoconch II, surface smooth, with a few rough growth lines towards the lip margin. Lip nearly straight, orthocline. H 0.32 mm, W 0.45 mm. Transition to teleoconch clear by change in sculpture (Figs. 42-44 of paratype 1).

Teleoconch - Spire broadly raised with three rounded whorls. Suture deep.

Remarks: Placement in the genus *Papuliscala* is based on the paucispiral protoconch and reticulated sculpture which are similar to other species from the Atlantic Ocean, and to the overall similarity with e.g. *P. cerithielloides* and *P. caroliennae* n. sp. except for the low spire and the presence of an umbilicus. Distinct features are the oblique nucleus of the protoconch and the continuing sculpture on the base of the whorl and open umbilicus. A somewhat similar species is *Papuliscala lydiae* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2017, only known from old shells on the Coral Patch Seamount, but that species lacks an umbilicus and it has hardly any sculpture on the base of the whorl.

It is possible that we are dealing with an undescribed genus characterised by a deviating paucispiral protoconch, open umbilicus and sculpture on the base of the whorl. A generic placement may be reconsidered once live-collected specimens are found and morphological and genetic analyses are available.

First whorl with about 20 oblique axial ribs. At about ½ whorl, four spiral cords develop on the peripheral whorl face. Overrunning axial ribs thickened at the crossings. Numerous prosocline growth lines visible. Axial ribs and growth lines at about 30° with spire axis. Second whorl with about 21 axial ribs and six spiral cords. Between axial ribs five to seven growth stages visible with major growth lines. The body whorl with about 30 axial ribs and 10 spiral cords, six above and four below the suture. The axial ribs strongly protruded near the lip margin (Fig. 12 of paratype 1), major inter-rib growth

Figures 40-44. *Papuliscala atlantisa* n. sp., Atlantis Seamount, M151/23404. 40, 41: holotype, H 2.8 mm, W 2.3 mm; 42-44: paratype 1, W 1.4 mm, protoconch H 0.32 mm, W 0.45 mm. Arrowheads = lip of the protoconch.

Figuras 40-44. Papuliscala atlantisa n. sp., Banco Atlantis, M151/23404. 40, 41: holotipo, H 2,8 mm, W 2,3 mm; 42-44: paratipo 1, W 1,4 mm, protoconcha H 0,32 mm, W 0,45 mm. Punta de flecha = labio de la protoconcha.

stages as fine secondary axial rib sculpture (Figs. 42-44).

Umbilicus open, deep and tortuous (Fig. 41); sculpture of axial ribs and spiral cords.

Aperture 50% of shell height, rounded, weakly angular at parietal end of columella (Fig. 40). Columella nearly straight in the centre. Columellar lip sharp, peristome damaged, prosocline. Columellar and labial callus smooth, thinning on parietal side, smooth inside whorl.

Variability: The shells show somewhat irregular growth stages. The holotype has two axial ridges like varices,

most paratypes have none. Height up to 4 mm.

Distribution: Only known from type locality (Fig. 2C).

Remarks: Placement in the genus *Papuliscala* is based on the same arguments as in *P. meteorica* n. sp. which is so similar that it is certainly congeneric. Distinct features of *P. atlantisa* are the simple smooth flattened protoconch, the continuing sculpture on the base of the whorl and the open umbilicus. *Papuliscala meteorica* n. sp. differs by a different protoconch, a less stout outline, a finer sculpture and a well demarcated umbilical area.

Figures 45-47. *Papuliscala vixcostata* n. sp., Atlantis Seamount, M151/23404. 45: holotype, H 4.2 mm, W 1.4 mm; 46, 47: paratype 1, H 4.2 mm, W 1.3 mm, protoconch 0.63 mm, W 0.48 mm. Arrowhead = lip of the protoconch.

Figuras 45-47. Papuliscala vixcostata n. sp., Banco Atlantis, M151/23404. 45: holotipo, H 4,2 mm, W 1,4 mm; 46, 47: paratipo 1, H 4,2 mm, W 1,3 mm, protoconcha 0,63 mm, W 0,48 mm. Punta de flecha = labio de la protoconcha.

The outline, size and sculpture of *P. atlantisae* n. sp. are similar to *Larsenia scalaroides* Warén, 1989. WARÉN (1989) tentatively placed that species in the family Vanikoridae but clearly considered Epitoniidae as a possible placement. *Larsenia*

scalaroides nevertheless clearly differs in having a rounded aperture with an arched columella (nearly straight in *P. atlantisae* n. sp.), in lacking any obvious spiral sculpture, and in having the axial ribs definitely continued inside the umbilicus.

Papuliscala vixcostata n. sp. (Figs. 2D, 45-47)

Type material: Holotype (shell, MNHN-IM-2000-35211, Fig. 45), paratype 1 (shell, MNHM-IM-2000-35211, Figs. 46-47) and two fragmentary paratype shells (SMF351093) from grab sample M151/23404, 21-X-2018.

Type locality: Atlantis Seamount, 33.971 °N – 30.206 °W, 677 m, in bioclastic sand with coral fragments.

Etymology: *vixcostata* refers to the weak axial sculpture.

Description (based on the holotype, Fig. 45): Shell with a highly-raised spire, fragile, smooth with sharp costae, blunt apex, colour white. H 4.2 mm, W 1.4 mm, spire angle 17°.

Protoconch – Single stage, paucispiral, raised shell with globular nucleus, 1

$\frac{3}{4}$ smooth whorls without protoconch II. Lip broken and integrated with teleoconch. H 0.63 mm, W 0.48 mm. Transition to teleoconch clear by change in sculpture (Fig. 47, paratype 1).

Teleoconch - Spire raised with 4 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, all whorls with sharp vertical ribs

Figures 48, 49. *Papuliscala mikra* n. sp., holotype, Great Meteor Seamount, M151/23425R6, H 1.4 mm, W 0.7 mm, protoconch I H 0.20 mm, W 0.28 mm, protoconch II W 0.29 mm. Large arrowhead = lip of protoconch I, small arrow = lip of protoconch II.

Figuras 48, 49. Papuliscala mikra n. sp., holotipo, Gran Banco Meteor, M151/23425R6, H 1,4 mm, W 0,7 mm, protoconcha I H 0,20 mm, W 0,28 mm, protoconcha II W 0,29 mm. Punta de flecha grande = labio de protoconcha I, flecha pequeña = labio de protoconcha II.

(costae) on the whorl face, about 14 on each whorl. Whorls concave below upper suture, slightly convex over the periphery and concave above lower suture. Whorl face smooth with fine growth lines. One strong spiral cord partly covered by the suture; forming a strong keel to base of whorl. Suture shallow, slightly impressed.

Base of body whorl slightly concave, without axial ribs, fine growth lines present. Umbilicus absent.

Aperture 20% of shell height, oval, slightly flared at base (Fig. 45). Columella oblique and curved, columellar lip distinct, outer lip (eroded), slightly flattened at the periphery, orthocline, nearly horizontal at its union with

penultimate whorl, partly covering spiral cord. Inside smooth.

Variability: Large protoconch and large shell fragments suggest that species can grow significantly larger than the holotype. No variability observed among the few available shells and fragments.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality (Fig. 2D).

Remarks: Distinct features are the smooth sculpture with axial costae. Similar species of *Papuliscala* are not known. Several species belonging to other genera of Epitoniidae have a similar axial structure but all these species have multispiral protoconchs.

Papuliscala mikra n. sp. (Figs. 2D, 48, 49)

Type material: Holotype (shell MNHN-IM-2000-35212, Figs. 48-49) from ROV sample M151/23425-R6, 25-X-2018.

Other material examined: Hyères Seamount - SMT2/DW182, 31.387 °N – 28.892 °W, 480 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, one shell (MNHN-IM-2014-7966).

Type locality: Great Meteor Seamount, 29.565 °N – 28.339 °W, 944 m, in bioclastic sand with coral fragments.

Etymology: *mikra* refers to small in Greek (mikro).

Description (based on the holotype, Fig. 48-49): Shell with a raised spire, fragile, smooth with sharp raised costae, globular apex, colour white, H 1.4 mm, W 0.7 mm, spire angle 24°.

Protoconch - Two-staged. Protoconch I, paucispiral, raised with globular nucleus, $\frac{3}{4}$ smooth whorl with growth lines. H 0.20 mm, W 0.26 mm. Protoconch II, $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl with five axial ribs with growth lines. H 0.30 mm, W 0.29 mm. Transition to teleoconch clear by change in sculpture (Fig. 49).

Teleoconch - Spire with three inflated whorls, all whorls with sharp near-vertical ribs (costae) on the whorl face. First whorl with 12 ribs, second whorl with 13 ribs, body whorl with 17 ribs. Whorl face smooth with fine growth lines. One strong spiral cord directly above lower suture; forming a strong keel to base of whorl. Suture shallow, impressed.

DISCUSSION

The genus *Papuliscala* includes 16 known species in the North Atlantic Ocean of which 11 were found in the SASC and 10 are described as new to science in this paper.

We distinguish three groups within NE Atlantic species of this genus according to their morphological shell characters: *Papuliscala elongata* (Watson, 1881), *P. praelonga* (Jeffreys, 1877), *P. tavianii* Bouchet & Warén, 1986, *P. lydiae* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2017, *P. dictyophora* n. sp., *P. seamountae* n. sp. and *P. platoensis* n. sp. form the “*elongata*” group whose members are likely a specific radiation that share a common ancestor. Surprisingly, the widespread species *P. elongata* was not found in the SASC. All members of this group have a coarse reticulated sculpture with oblique, yet nearly straight, axial ribs. *Papuliscala lydiae*, *P. seamountae* n. sp. and *P. platoensis* n. sp. lack a protoconch II whereas *P. elongata*, *P. praelonga*, *P. tavianii* and *P. dictyophora* n. sp. have a short protoconch II with axial ribs. *Papuliscala cerithielloides* Bouchet & Warén, 1986, *P. caroliensae* n. sp., *P. luuki* n. sp. and *P. daani* n. sp. form

Whorl base concave below the keel, slightly convex near the columella. Basal area with numerous irregular growth lines. Umbilicus absent.

Aperture 30% of shell height, circular (Fig. 48). Columella curved, columellar lip inconspicuous, peristome broken, joint of peristome with penultimate whorl sloping.

Distribution: The Great Meteor- and Hyères Seamounts, 29.5 – 31.4 °N, 28.3 – 28.9 °W, 480 – 944 m (Fig. 2D).

Remarks: Distinct features are the smooth sculpture with raised axial costae. *Papuliscala vixcostata* n. sp. has much weaker costae and a different protoconch. *Cylindriscala acus* (Watson, 1883) and *Cylindriscala vicina* (Dautzenberg & de Bourry, 1897) in Epitoniidae have a very similar axial structure but these species have multispiral protoconchs. Both species in *Cylindriscala* are known from the Azores.

the “*cerithielloides*” group with a finely reticulated sculpture with flexuous axial ribs. The first three species have paucispiral protoconchs with about 1 $\frac{1}{4}$ smooth whorls and lack a protoconch II. *Papuliscala daani* n. sp. also has a paucispiral protoconch but has a short protoconch II. *Papuliscala meteorica* n. sp. and *Papuliscala atlantisa* n. sp. form the small “*meteorica*” group with a specific radiation across the SASC; distinctive features include an umbilicus and a flattened protoconch. The remaining 14 species of *Papuliscala* have a flattened base of the whorl without significant sculpture, and no umbilicus. *Papuliscala vixcostata* n. sp. and *P. mikra* n. sp. share no common group with similar features, and may be the last representatives of branches of extinct taxa.

It is remarkable that ten new taxa in *Papuliscala* were found whereas the genus only included eight extant species to date. It can be expected that several more taxa are to be discovered in the SASC in view of the limited sampling carried out in that huge area of sea bottom and the low number of speci-

mens found in some new taxa. Little is known about the soft parts, microhabitats and food requirements of *Papuliscala*. Epitoniids are known to feed on cnidarians (ROBERTSON, 1963, 1970; PATZNER, 2004) and *Papuliscala* most likely shares this trait. Additional studies with live-collected specimens may clarify the systematics and evolution of this group.

An interesting observation is that the majority of species in the genus are only known from their empty shells; frequently looking fresh but often old remains. It may be that some of these taxa are extinct. Deep-water scleractinians were flourishing during the glaciation periods of the Pleistocene in more southern regions of the North Atlantic for example on the continental slopes of NW Africa (FOUBERT *ET AL.*, 2008, WIENBERG *ET AL.*, 2010, 2018; HEBBELN *ET AL.*, 2019), the Azores (BRAGA-HENRIQUES *ET AL.*, 2013), the Galicia Bank (SOMOZA *ET AL.*, 2014; ALTUNA, 2017), Bay of Biscay (REVEILLAUD *ET AL.*, 2008) and in the western (WANG *ET AL.*, 2019) and central Mediterranean (VERTINO, STOLARSKI, BOSELLINI & TAVIANI, 2014). During the warmer interglacial periods and since the onset of the Holocene, the most favourable area for living scleractinians shifted north in the NE Atlantic, to off western Ireland and Norway (FRANK *ET AL.*, 2011). The skeletal remains of scleractinians form a prolific settling ground for other cnidarians like Octocorallia, Hydrozoa, Actiniaria and more Scleractinia. Living taxa in these classes are still present on the slopes of the Seamounts in the SASC but they must have been more abundant during the glaciation periods in the Pleistocene when the Azores Current followed a more southern route and the sea level was significantly lower (WIENBERG *ET AL.*, 2010). The food source and food diversity for epitoniids was probably more plentiful during these glaciation periods. Some taxa, including some species in *Papuliscala*, may not have survived the environmental changes in habitat during the glaciations and warmer periods in the Pleistocene. Changes in molluscan fauna during the

Pleistocene and since the onset of the Holocene were also discussed for DWC habitats off Mauritania concerning to the family Fissurellidae Fleming, 1822 (HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2018), and the genera *Chauvetia* Monterosato, 1884 (HOFFMAN, FRAUSSEN & FREIWALD, 2018) and *Calliostoma* Swainson, 1840 (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2019). These carnivorous taxa were found in biocoenoses rich in cnidarians and in sediment with scleractinian remains.

According to their protoconchs, some of the species here described have a larval development with a short free lecithotrophic phase (i.e. *P. dictyophora*, *P. daani*, *P. meteorica* and *P. mikra*). The previously known species *P. praelonga*, *P. elongata* and *P. tavianii* also have this type of larval development. The other species here described seem to have a direct development without a free pelagic phase (*P. seamountae*, *P. caroliense*, *P. platoensis*, *P. luuki*, *P. atlantica* and *P. vixcostata*) as well as the previously described *P. lydiae*.

LOZOUET (1999: 20) described *Papuliscala ambulata* from the Upper Oligocene (23–34 Ma) with a multi-spiral, axially-ribbed protoconch indicative of a planktotrophic development. LANDAU, CEULEMANS & VAN DINGENEN (2018: 206–208) described *Papuliscala redoniensis* and *P. presselierenensis* from the Upper Miocene (Tortonian 7.2–11.6 Ma) with a two-stage protoconch in both species similar to the extant *P. elongata* suggesting a lecithotrophic larval development. Planktotrophic larval development in combination with internal fertilization represents an important evolutionary innovation of Caenogastropoda (PONDER *ET AL.*, 2008). This type of development is retained by most epitoniids, such as in the genera *Narrimania* and *Eccliseogyra* (see PIMENTA *ET AL.*, 2018), very close to *Papuliscala*, all of them previously included in Nystiellidae. Nevertheless, *Papuliscala* alongside with the close *Murdochella* have lost the planktotrophic larval stage (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1986), and thus the protoconch lacks the typical strong sculpturing characteristic of the former Nystiellinae. The evolutionary transition from a planktotrophic larval

development to lecithotrophic and then direct development has occurred on multiple occasions and in many lineages of caenogastropods (PONDER *ET AL.*, 2008), but the opposite path is not positively documented (see STRATHMANN, 1978, 1985; COLLIN & MORAN, 2018). According to the fossil record the genus *Papuliscala* probably had developed lecithotrophy by the Miocene and this type of development remained until present, and some lineages subsequently evolve to direct development.

A short planktonic phase may allow spreading of the species across the seamounts in the SASC and possibly across the Azores in a stepwise dispersal, but eventually long distances between seamounts turn into insurmountable barriers for survival. A planktonic development phase, like is common in most other epitoniid genera, is clearly a more reliable survival trait in a changing environment (JABLONSKI, 1986). The advantage of a direct or very short larval development clearly is that offspring is placed directly near their favorable habitat and food source and the larval survival rate will in general be higher to that in a planktonic development. The downside is that such species could be prone to extinction when the habitat disappears (JABLONSKI & LUTZ, 1983). The Pleistocene sequences of warming and cooling must have been particularly stressful for species with a short larval development phase.

We consider the ten new species as endemics to the SASC. The distances that separate some seamounts from others or from the nearest continental shelf implies that they function as "islands" from the biogeographic point of view, since many species that live in them cannot inhabit the bathyal or abyssal bottoms that surround them nor reach the seamounts through long distance dispersion processes (GOFAS, 2007). Likewise many authors have considered seamounts as "hotspots" of species richness and centers of endemism (i.e. REID, 1998; CASTELIN *ET AL.*, 2010, 2011; SHANK, 2010). The data here provided corroborate these assessments. Notwithstanding

one debated questions about the biodiversity importance of seamounts is whether they are "hotspots" and/or "stepping stones" for marine fauna (SAMADI *ET AL.*, 2006). Anyway, given the biological interest of seamounts and due the multiple human impacts they suffer, protection measures are urgently needed for these enclaves (GUBBAY, 2003; MORATO *ET AL.*, 2010; SERRÃO SANTOS, TEMPERA & MORATO, 2010). GOFAS (2002) reviewed the highly-isolated endemics in *Trituba* (Cerithiopsidae) and he concluded that a seamount separation in excess to 200 km is not passable for most species of this genus.

Despite their non-planktotrophic development, *Papuliscala elongata* and *P. praelonga* have amphi-atlantic distributions (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1986; PIMENTA *ET AL.*, 2018) and *P. cerithielloides* has a relatively wide NE Atlantic distribution (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1986; HOFFMAN, VAN HEUGTEN & LAVALEYE., 2011). How these species have been capable of bridging gaps in excess of 1000 km in a planktonic phase to spread across the Atlantic is still unexplained. Assuming an average current velocity of 1 m/s this represents a travel time in excess of 12 days, which is beyond what is considered feasible for the life span of lecithotrophic larvae, i.e. from a few hours to a few days.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Crews and scientific staffs of cruises SEAMOUNT 2 (R/V SUROIT), POS397 (R/V POSEIDON) and M151 (R/V METEOR) are thanked for their dedication in collecting the samples used in this study. Kai Horst George and Achim Wehrmann yielded access to the material of cruise POS397. Nicol Mahnken is acknowledged for sample retention at SaM and for preparing SEM samples. Technical assistants of Senckenberg am Meer sorted the live-collected material from POS397. We are grateful to the (anonymous) reviewers for improving our manuscripts. POS397 and M151 were funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft.

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